

IPBES invasive alien species assessment, data management report for Chapter 3. Section 3.3.4.6: Sea level rise

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Project leader and contributors:

- Ryan Blanchard (rblanchard@csir.co.za)

Data curator(s):

- Ryan Blanchard (rblanchard@csir.co.za)

- Ryoko Kawakami (r-kawakami@iges.or.jp)

Description

Section 3.3.4.6 assesses the role of sea level rise as a driver of biological invasions for chapter 3 of IPBES thematic assessment of invasive alien species and their control. The experts conducted a systematic review to report on the existing knowledge on this driver. This systematic review consists in the main source of evidence for the section.

Process overview

Search 1:

Search 2:

Search 3:

Search 4:

Search 5

Additional papers added to the selection (experts' knowledge and reviewers' recommendations) n=8

Papers selected for review n=25

Protocol

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** literature review

- **Search language(s):** English

- **Search terms:**

Search 1: "Climate Change" AND "Sea level rise" AND invasive OR exotic -> 22500 hits downloaded all on first page – selected 2

Search 2: "sea level rise" AND "invasive OR Exotic OR non-native" AND "salinity" AND "spread" 2500 – 3

Search 3: "sea level rise" AND "invasive species" AND "salt water intrusion" OR "salinity" – 7

Search 4: "sea level rise" AND "Driver" AND "invasive OR exotic" AND "spread" 5300 selected – 3

Search 5: "Sea level rise" AND invasive OR exotic AND arctic or antarctic – 10400 – 2 selected

Reference added by experts added and snowball searching– 8

Background references – 9

- **Search engine:**

Search 1 and 3: Web of science

Search 2, 4 and 5: Google Scholar

- **Date:** August 2019 to November 2019; March 2020

- **Overview of the search results and selection criteria:**

Number of search result: 17

Search 1: 2 selected

Search 2: 3 selected

Search 3: 7 selected

Search 4: 3 selected

Search 5: 2 selected

Selection criteria:

For all 5 searches, titles were screened from the first 5 pages, potential papers were downloaded and 17 papers were selected for review. 9 papers were selected for background information. Additional references were found by searching for specific items based on under represented taxa or regions through targeted searches e.g. arctic or antarctic.

Number of added papers (experts' knowledge and reviewers' recommendations): An additional 8 papers were added by experts.

- **Step by step analysis (methodology, categories, etc.):**

Number of papers reviewed: 25 (See Chapter 3_literature_review_masterdatabase.xlsx)

Fields extracted:

- Publication title

- Year of publication

- Invasion stage [Uptake and transport; Introduction; Establishment; Spread]
- Biomes [Terrestrial; Freshwater; Marine]
- Taxon [Plant; Vertebrate; Invertebrate; Microbes]
- Type of study [Primary study; Review; Meta-analysis]
- Region [Europe and Central Asia; Asia-Pacific; Oceania; Americas; Africa]
- Unit of analysis [IPBES units of analysis]
- Cross-cutting theme [Scenarios and models; indigenous and local knowledge; Good quality of life]
- Comment (free text)

- **Files (code, review templates, etc.):**

Chapter 3_literature_review_masterdatabase.xlsx